

METHODS USED IN TEACHING THROUGH TRANSLANGUAGING

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the analysis of current publications in English-language scientific periodicals, which present the use of translanguaging as a pedagogical method or tool, including in school and university classes when studying languages or specialized subjects in a foreign*

Keywords: *translingualism, pedagogy, linguodidactics, subject-language integrated learning.*

INTRODUCTION

Foreign authors generally unanimously associate the origin of the term "translingualism" with the pedagogical practice of the Welsh linguodidact K. Williams, who, when working with bilinguals, used a combination of two languages in the educational process: for example, he asked students a question in one language and allowed them to give an answer in another language. Subsequently, K. Baker translated Williams' term trawsieithu into English, receiving the concept of translanguaging. The starting point of modern research on translingualism is thus considered to be the work of the Welsh specialist, but a broader and more active discussion of translingualism began in the 21st century.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

At the turn of the first and second decades of the 21st century, the idea of translingualism was picked up and actively developed, in particular, by American authors, who saw in it an interesting pedagogical perspective for teaching children of various ethnic and cultural backgrounds arriving in the United States with immigrant parents. It seems to us that scientists from the City University of New York, whose research team we, for our own convenience, collectively call the New York School of Translingualism, were especially proactive in this regard. It is to them that the overwhelming majority of English-language authors writing about translingualism over the past decade refer, and we will use the ideas of the New Yorkers as the structural basis of this article.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Translanguaging refers to the practice of using different languages interchangeably in the learning process. This includes switching between languages while reading, writing, speaking, and even listening, with the purpose of understanding concepts more deeply. Translanguaging is not just about code-switching; it is a pedagogical tool that acknowledges the cognitive and social resources students draw from multiple languages to make meaning. This approach aligns with a more inclusive, student-centered pedagogy that promotes bilingual or multilingual students' linguistic skills.

Code-Switching Between Languages

One of the most common methods in translanguaging is code-switching, where learners alternate between languages within a conversation, sentence, or even a word. For instance, an English-Spanish bilingual student may switch from English to Spanish to clarify a concept or express a thought that feels more accurate in the second language. Teachers can encourage students to use the most comfortable language for them when explaining their ideas, thus promoting a richer understanding of content [3].

Example: A teacher discussing a math concept in English might allow students to explain it in their home language, fostering both comprehension and confidence.

Bilingual Texts and Resources

Teachers can provide students with bilingual resources such as books, handouts, or digital materials in both the students' first language and the target language. This method supports comprehension and enables students to connect concepts across languages. For example, reading a story in both English and their native language helps students understand the vocabulary and narrative structure in both languages.

Example: Students might read a story in English and simultaneously have access to a translation in their home language. Afterward, they discuss the plot or themes using whichever language is more accessible.

Collaborative Learning in Multiple Languages

Collaborative tasks in which students work together using multiple languages are an effective translanguaging strategy. Pairing multilingual students allows them to exchange ideas in their preferred languages, enriching discussions and helping each other understand concepts. This promotes language development in all languages involved and reinforces the idea that all languages are valuable tools for learning.

Example: In a science class, students can work in pairs, discussing their observations of a scientific experiment in both English and their home language, allowing them to compare ideas and solidify their understanding [3].

Using Visuals to Support Multilingual Discussions

Translanguaging often includes visual aids like diagrams, charts, and pictures that bridge linguistic gaps. By integrating visuals into lessons, teachers provide a universal language that all students can relate to, regardless of the languages they speak. Visuals act as a point of reference when switching between languages and can help students clarify or reinforce what they have learned.

Example: A lesson on weather patterns can include visuals like weather maps or infographics that students can explain in any language, facilitating clearer communication and understanding of scientific terms.

Benefits of Translanguaging in Education

Enhancing Understanding

Translanguaging supports deeper cognitive engagement by allowing students to access and connect knowledge in all the languages they know. It helps bridge gaps in understanding that may exist when only one language is used [4].

Building Confidence

When students are encouraged to use their home language, it helps reduce anxiety and boosts their confidence. They no longer feel pressured to exclusively use the target language, making them more willing to participate.

CONCLUSION

Translanguaging represents a shift in the way language is viewed in educational settings. Rather than seeing students' multiple languages as barriers, translanguaging views them as resources that can enhance learning. By allowing students to use all the languages at their disposal, teachers can create a more inclusive, dynamic, and effective learning environment. This approach not only promotes deeper understanding but also empowers multilingual students by validating their linguistic identities and fostering a positive learning experience.

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